

THE KEY COMPONENTS OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AND THEIR ROLE FOR EFFECTIVELY COMMUNICATING OF LEARNERS

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Annotation: This article discusses the communicative competence and its components such as linguistic, strategic, discursive, and socio-cultural and distinguishes the concept of "competence". Besides the professional skills, essential to a successful career, individuals also need to acquire the communicative competency, which is equally important as it includes various other competencies, such as: linguistic, social, socio-cultural, or strategic competences in order to communicate and interact with each other. Our article aims at discussing the different ways and methods teachers can use in the language classroom.

Keywords: communicative competence, competence, linguistic, social, socio-cultural, strategic, knowledge, skills, abilities, ideas, professional, discursive

Today one of the most accepted frameworks of teaching foreign languages is the communicative language teaching, which aims to develop students' communicative competence. The communicative competence represents the linguistic system that students should use effectively and appropriately in the target language and culture, in other words, the ability to understand and use the language to communicate successfully in authentic environments. Competence, one of the most controversial notions in linguistics, has been introduced by the American linguist Noam Chomsky in 1965, in his influential book *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax*. He makes the distinction between competence seen as the speaker-hearer's knowledge of his language and performance, which is the use of language in real

situations. This distinction has led to attempts to broaden the concept of linguistic competence by taking into account the sociolinguistic aspects of the language.

Currently, there are different interpretations of the term "communicative competence", there is no single definition of it. Initially, the term defined the ability necessary to perform linguistic activity in the native language. According to N. Chomsky, competent speaker or listener must understand an unlimited number of sentences according to models, and also have a judgment about the utterance, that is, see formal similarities and differences in the two languages. In relation to teaching foreign languages, this concept has been developed in detail within the framework of studies conducted by the Council of Europe to establish the level of foreign language proficiency (Strasbourg, 1996), and is defined as the ability to perform any activity based on the knowledge, skills, abilities, and work experience acquired during training [2].

The concepts of capacity and competence are different notions. Competence refers to the ability to perform any activity, including speech. Capacity is a meaningful component of such an ability in the form of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired during training. A.V. Khutorskoy understands competence as a set of interrelated personality qualities set in relation to a certain range of subjects and processes [11]. M. N. Vyatyutnev defines communicative competence "as the choice of the implementation of speech behavior programs depending on the ability to navigate in a particular communication environment; the ability to classify situations depending on the topic, tasks, communicative attitudes that arise in students before the conversation, as well as during the conversation in the process of mutual adaptation" [7]. I. A. Zimnaya defines competence as "internal, potential, hidden psychological new formation: knowledge, ideas, action programs, value systems and relationships, which are then revealed in human competencies" [8].

N. I. Gez gives the following definition of communicative competence: "communicative competence is the ability of a person to understand and generate foreign-language utterances in a variety of socially determined situations, taking into

account linguistic and social rules that native speakers adhere to" [9]. Communicative competence in its modern interpretation includes the following types of competencies: linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive, strategic, social, socio-cultural, subject, professional. Let us look at each of the components in more detail. Linguistic competences are related to the use of language through the expression and interpretation of concepts, thoughts, feelings, facts, and opinions in order to perform oral and written discussions. Such interactions may take place in diverse social and cultural contexts, which will determine the characteristics of the language written or spoken, such as the grammar, pragmatic, and sociolinguistic characteristics.

Linguistic competences are highly related to communication competences and they are even seen as equal. Within scientific production and communication, linguistic competences are related to the adequate use of language.

Sociolinguistic competence is the ability to communicate appropriately by using the right words, expressions, and attitude towards a specific topic, setting, and relationship. Sociolinguistic competence means knowing how to use and respond to language appropriately, given the setting, the topic, and the relationships among the people communicating. Sociolinguistic competence asks: Which words and phrases fit this setting and this topic? How can I express a specific attitude (courtesy, authority, friendliness, respect)? When I need to? How do I know what attitude another person is expressing?

Sociocultural competence is an ability to communicate in a language appropriately, situationally and culturally. It is the knowledge of customs, rules, beliefs and principles of a given society. Sociocultural factors influence people's feelings, values, beliefs, behaviors, attitudes, and interactions. The formation of this competence is carried out in the context of a dialogue of cultures, taking into account differences in the socio-cultural perception of the world and ultimately contributes to the formation of a "secondary linguistic personality".

Social competence consists of social, emotional, cognitive, and behavioral skills needed for successful social adaptation. Social competence

also reflects having the ability to take another's perspective concerning a situation, learn from past experiences, and apply that learning to the changes in social interactions[5].

Social competence is the foundation upon which expectations for future interaction with others are built and perceptions of an individual's own behavior are developed. Social competence frequently encompasses social skills, social communication, and interpersonal communication [5]. Competence is directly connected to social behavior, such as social motives, abilities, skills, habits, and knowledge. All of these social factors contribute to the development of a person's behavior [6]. Strategic competence is a competence with which a student can fill in gaps in language knowledge, as well as speech and social experience of communication in a foreign language environment. Discursive competence means the ability to use and interpret the forms of words and their meanings to create coherent texts, generate coherent foreign language utterances, logically, consistently and convincingly build your speech, the ability to choose the right communication strategy. Subject competence is the ability to navigate in a meaningful way of communication in a certain area of human activity. Professional competence is acquired in the course of training and provides the ability for successful professional activity. It includes knowledge from the fields of sciences that are significant for professional activity; personal qualities that ensure the effectiveness of professional activity.

N. I. Gez identifies three components of communicative competence: – linguistic component — knowledge about the system of the studied language and the skills of operating lexico-grammatical and phonetic means of communication formed on their basis; – pragmatic component — knowledge, skills and abilities that allow understanding and generating foreign language utterances in accordance with a specific communication situation, speech task and communicative intent; – sociolinguistic component — knowledge, skills and abilities that allow speech and non-speech communication with native speakers of the studied language in

accordance with the national and cultural characteristics of a foreign linguosocium[9]. V. V. Safonova identifies the following components of communicative competence: linguistic (grammatical, linguistic); speech (pragmatic, strategic, discursive); socio-cultural (sociolinguistic, linguo-cultural) competence [10].

M. Canale and M. Swain distinguish four components of communicative competence: grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discursive competence, strategic competence [1]. Jan Van Eck identifies such components as: linguistic, sociocultural, sociolinguistic, strategic, discursive, social [3]. J. Savignon in his research describes four components: grammatical, sociolinguistic, compensatory and the competence of speech strategy [4].

Thus, analyzing the domestic and foreign literature, we can conclude that communicative competence is a complex phenomenon in the methodology of teaching foreign languages and requires new approaches to solving the problem of its essence and variable component composition.

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